

Church of Saint Demetrios

also known as “Cathedral (Metropolis) of Mystras”

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Peloponnese, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Language, Religious Place, Graeco-Phrygian, Mystras, Orthodoxy, Greek

The Metropolitan church (Cathedral) of Mystras and seat of the Diocese of Lacedaemonia (up to the first years after the liberation of Greece from the Ottomans) is dedicated to Saint Demetrios. It is situated in the north-east part of the lower city of the settlement, close to the main gate and within the complex of buildings known as the Metropolis. It dates to the second half of the 13th century. It is the earliest among the surviving late-byzantine churches of Mystras, built in the form of a wooden-roofed basilica. It was probably founded by Bishop Eugenios (1262-1272), depicted in the diakonikon (area south of the sanctuary), where is located also his tomb. Theodosios (1272-1283?), Eugenios' successor, commanded a large portion of the wall paintings of the church. Theodosios was also depicted in the church, kneeling before the Virgin in the conch of the apse of the sanctuary. His portrait was later scratched off, most probably because he was a supporter of the Union of the Greek and the Roman Churches. However, the carved inscriptions mention Nikephoros Moschopoulos as the founder of Saint Demetrios. To Moschopoulos hand is also attributed part of the frescoes of the church, including the figures of the apostles in the south aisle, painted sometime in the end of the 13th century. Later, around 1310, in the narthex more scenes were painted, including those of the Second Coming and of the Oecumenical Councils, following the latest stylistic trends of Palaeologan art. In the first half of the 15th century galleries were added to the church under Bishop Matthaios, as mentioned by a relief inscription. It was then that the monument took its final form, belonging to the so-called "mixed type of Mystras", which combines the three-aisled basilica plan on the ground floor and the five-domed, cross-in-square plan in the upper part, with three three-sided arches to the east. According to tradition, the last Byzantine emperor Constantine XI Palaiologos was crowned at the church in 1449. The embossed double-headed eagle of the Palaiologos family on the floor of Saint Demetrios, under the dome, is believed to have been the exact spot where the coronation has taken place. The last renovations of the monument were associated with the supposed coronation of Constantine Palaiologos, a hypothesis that does not appear to be supported by the sources. The exterior wall paintings of the north portico, depicting four deceased metropolitans of the 14th and early 15th centuries, have also been associated with Bishop Matthaios. The complex of the Metropolis is composed as well of structures added later: the tower-shaped bell tower (southeast corner), arched porticos (west facade and north side), a north courtyard with arches and two-storey structures (north), at the instigation of Bishop Ananias, who was slaughtered by the Ottomans in 1760. The sculptural decoration of the church is from different periods and thus varies in style. The most significant examples are the carved iconostasis, the sculptural elements of which date to c.1200 and were reused, having originally belonged to an unknown church of the southern Peloponnese; the two proskynetaria with relief designs; the architrave from the time of Bishop Matthaios, with designs carved in porous stone and the parapets in the frieze of the upper room. The name of the aforementioned Bishop also appears (abbreviated) on the proskynetaria of the iconostasis. Within the complex of the Metropolis was created a Museum where are exhibited selected objects and artefacts from the Byzantine period from Mystras and Sparta.

Date Range: 1260 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Saint Demetrios

Region tags: Peloponnese, Mystras, Greece

The Metropolitan church (Cathedral) of Saint Demetrios of Mystras, in Peloponnese, Greece

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chatzidakis, M. “Νεώτερα Για Την Ιστορία Και Την Τέχνη Της Μητρόπολης Του Μυστρά.” Δελτίον Της Χριστιανικής Αρχαιολογικής Εταιρείας 9 (1977-1979), 143-179.
- Source 2: Marinou, G. Άγιος Δημήτριος. Η Μητρόπολη Του Μυστρά. Athens: Unpublished PhD dissertation, National Technical University of Athens, 1990.
- Source 3: Manousakas, M. “Η Χρονολογία Της Κτιτορικής Επιγραφής Του Αγίου Δημητρίου Του Μυστρά.” ΔΧΑΕ 4, no. 1 (1959).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/metropolis-mystras>
- Source 1 Description: Detailed description and photographs of the Cathedral of Saint Demetrios, Mystras
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=14543
- Source 2 Description: Description of Saint Demetrios by the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports
- Source 3 URL: <https://youtu.be/DgaAjXKv68U>
- Source 3 Description: A video about Saint Demetrios

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The settlement of Mystras to which the church belongs is built on a hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Mound

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: Although the settlement of Mystras is quite small, the church is located within the walls that surround it

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Although the settlement of Mystras is quite small, the church is located within the walls that surround it

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The church is located within the walled settlement of Mystras

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The complex of the Metropolis is composed as well of structures added after the construction of the church. The tower-shaped bell tower (southeast corner), arched porticos (west facade and north side), a north courtyard with the arches and two-storey structures (north)

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The church was built in the form of a wooden-roofed basilica. In the first half of the 15th century, galleries were added to the church under Bishop Matthaios. It was then that the monument took its final form, belonging to the so-called "mixed type of Mystras", which combines the three-aisled basilica plan on the ground floor and the five-domed, cross-in-square plan in the upper part, with three three-sided arches to the east.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The tower-shaped bell tower (southeast corner), arched porticos (west facade and north side), a north courtyard with arches and two-storey structures (north) were added later to the church.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The church built in the form of a wooden-roofed basilica. In the first half of the 15th century, galleries were added to the church under Bishop Matthaios. It was then that the monument took its final form, belonging to the so-called "mixed type of Mystras", which combines the three-aisled basilica plan on the ground floor and the five-domed, cross-in-square plan in the upper part, with three three-sided arches to the east.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The church had originally the form of a wooden-roofed basilica. In the first half of the 15th century, galleries were added to the church. It was then that the monument took its final form, belonging to the so-called "mixed type of Mystras", which combines the three-aisled basilica plan on the ground floor and the five-domed, cross-in-square plan in the upper part, with three three-sided arches to the east.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church was built for the worship of God. The church is dedicated to Saint Demetrios

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The church was built for the worship of God. The church is dedicated to Saint Demetrios

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: The church was built for the worship of God

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: The church was built for the worship of God

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: The church is the oldest one of the settlement of Mystras, so most probably it was built for responding to the spiritual needs of the habitants of Mystras

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: The church was erected by Bishop Eugenios. It was the first church built in Mystras, so it was most probable built for responding to the needs of the habitants of the settlement

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Notes: Saint Demetrios belongs in fact to the complex of the Metropolis of Mystras, composed as well of structures added later: the tower-shaped bell tower (southeast corner), arched porticos (west facade and north side), a north courtyard with arches and two-storey structures (north)

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The structures of the complex of the Metropolis of Mystras are attached to each other

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The church is the centre and most important part of the structure

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Earth

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments and binders used for the frescoes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments and binders

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: North portico: depictions of deceased Bishops. Brickwork and carved decorative elements

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Frescoes, carved elements, mosaic flooring

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Icons (panel paintings)

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim, seraphim

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Virgin Mary, Hierarchs, Bishops, Saints and other persons populating the narrative scenes depicted in the church

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are included in the narrative scenes depicted in the church

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The reliefs are purely decorative and have floral decoration. The embossed double-headed eagle of the Palaiologos family on the floor of the church, under the dome, is believed to have been the very place where the coronation has taken place.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints. On the outside of the church are also depicted Bishops

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints. There are also depictions of the Oecumenical Councils

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox churches are always informative, providing information on the persons and scenes depicted; or in other cases informing about the foundation of the monument

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Monograms of Bishops who have played a role in the construction and/or decoration of the church can also be found therein

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: The carved iconostasis of the church was made of sculptural elements from an unknown church

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, seraphim and cherubim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Around 1310 in the narthex was painted the scene of the Second Coming of the Lord

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses, Second Coming of the Lord, Oecumenical Councils

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The iconographic programme of the church includes as well depictions of the Oecumenical councils and of deceased Bishops

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Bishop Eugenios (1262-72), depicted in the diakonikon, where is located also his tomb, was buried in the church

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Bishop Eugenios (1262-72), depicted in the diakonikon, where is located also his tomb, was buried in the church

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: No, however, persons come to the church for praying to and worshipping God

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: No, however, persons come to the church for praying to and worshipping God

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, persons come to the church for praying to and worshipping God

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Services and other Orthodox rituals

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: The church is a functioning one, so rituals may/do take place there

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Impossible to specify

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Impossible to know, since the settlement where the church is located was abandoned and is an archaeological site

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: If services are taking place at the church, they follow the Christian Orthodox rite

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: If services are taking place at the church, they follow the Christian Orthodox rite

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings can vary from very precious objects or lands to daily-life objects or food.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings can vary from very precious objects or lands to daily-life objects or food.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Material offerings to Christian Orthodox churches and Monasteries can vary from very precious objects or lands to daily-life objects or food

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the place is required since the church dates to the 13th century and necessitates constant monitoring for its conservation and preservation

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Conservation works and periodic repairs are indeed required since the church dates to the 13th century

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Experts under the direction of the Hellenic Ministry of Culture are working on the preservation, conservation and generally the maintenance of the church

Other

– Other [specify]: Experts from various fields are collaborating and working together under the supervision of the Hellenic Ministry of Culture for the preservation, conservation and generally the maintenance of the church

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: The church is not a place of pilgrimage per se. However, every Orthodox consecrated church can potentially be considered a place of pilgrimage

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: The church celebrates on the feast day of Saint Demetrios, on the 26th of October.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: Not anymore, since the settlement to which the church is found is not anymore a living space

but an archaeological site

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Hellenic Ministry of Culture

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Chatzidakis, M.. "Νεώτερα Για Την Ιστορία Και Την Τέχνη Της Μητρόπολης Του Μυστρά". Δελτίον Της Χριστιανικής Αρχαιολογικής Εταιρείας 9 (1977).

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Marinou, G.. Άγιος Δημήτριος. Η Μητρόπολη Του Μυστρά. Athens: Unpublished PhD dissertation, National Technical University of Athens, 1990.

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Dufrenne, S.. "Les Programmes Iconographiques Des Églises Byzantines De Mystra". Cahiers Archéologiques 4 (1970): 5-8.

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Manousakas, M.. "Η Χρονολογία Της Κτιτορικής Επιγραφής Του Αγίου Δημητρίου Του Μυστρά". ΔΧΑΕ 4, no. 1 (1959).

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Millet, G.. Monuments Byzantins De Mistra. Paris, 1910.

Reference: Church of Saint Demetrios, Runciman, S.. Mistra. London, 1980.